

Explosion of Oxy-hydrogen Mixtures in Soap Bubbles.

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The ignition temperature of inflammable gas mixtures has been determined in various ways, *e.g.*, (i) by enclosing or passing the gas mixture into a heated vessel ; (ii) by direct contact with a hot surface at any point of the inflammable mixture ; (iii) igniting by adiabatic compression ; (iv) by an electric spark.

In (ii) and (iv) almost instantaneous ignition is secured, while in the other methods a time-lag is present. To secure instantaneous ignition, soap bubbles full of inflammable gas mixtures were ignited by McDavid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 1003) by touching these bubbles with a hot surface. The divergence in the results obtained by different authors is to be referred to the different methods adopted to cause ignition. The irreproducibility of McDavid's figures using different sources of ignition indicates the futility of attempts to establish ignition temperatures, as a physical constant, unless under similarly maintained conditions. The maintenance of exactly similar conditions in the ignition of gaseous mixtures, is hardly feasible in practical problems of mine explosions, and other similar accidents. The stationary method of ignition is of considerable practical importance, but the determination of the lowest ignition temperature under such circumstances is of still greater consequence.

In the present paper we have determined the effect of the volume of soap bubbles on their ignition temperatures. The ignition was effected by touching the soap bubbles either by an electrically heated platinum point formed by bending a wire at an acute angle, or by a platinum spiral (Chatterjee and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 441). We have, further, investigated the effect of the length of the platinum wire on the ignition temperature. By varying the platinum wires or using the same wire after roughening it by gently filing, or platinising it, or poisoning it by sulphuretted hydrogen we have come to the conclusion that this method of finding the ignition temperature of an inflammable gas mixture in soap bubbles is unreliable on account of the catalytic effect of the wires.

The temperature of the point or the spiral of platinum wire was determined by reference to a curve plotted with the currents necessary to melt known substances against their respective melting points when they are placed on the platinum point or spiral. The platinum point or spiral is enclosed on all sides except the front by a card board box. The working room has an asbestos ceiling and the doors and windows are kept closed thereby minimising air-currents during the experiment. Each day, however, fresh calibrations were made, although it was found possible to work several days with the same calibration if the wire was not changed, or the atmospheric condition did not change considerably.

In order to ensure reproducibility of results, the volume of the soap bubble had to be kept the same. For this, a special apparatus was devised (*vide, supra*) which enabled us to secure identical volumes and to vary the volumes of the soap bubbles as desired.

The heating current was measured accurately with a standard resistance and a standard cell by the potentiometric method. A set of secondary batteries was used for heating the platinum wire. The volume of the bubbles was controlled by the apparatus (Fig. 1) described below :

Fig. 1.

A is a 5-litre aspirator and V a graduated tube holding 1 litre. The whole apparatus is first filled with water and gas is then admitted through *d* until most of the water is displaced, the thistle-funnel *F* being temporarily removed. In order to blow a bubble, *e* is closed, *b* and *d* are opened with the mouth of *F* just on the surface of the soap solution and water is run from *T* to a given mark on *V*, *a* serving to regulate the flow, and the excess gas being allowed to escape. *F* is then removed from the solution with a film over its end and a bubble of required size blown by admitting the corresponding quantity of water into *V*. When all the gas in *V* has been used, a further supply is admitted from the aspirator by opening *e*.

A bottle was filled to about three fourths of its capacity with distilled water. One volume of glycerine was added to 3 volumes of a 2½ p.c. sodium oleate solution, shaken vigorously and kept in the dark for a week. In making large bubbles, sodium oleate weighing about one twentieth of the water taken was found more suitable.

With variations in the oxygen hydrogen ratio, the formation of hydrogen peroxide and ozone was indicated. An approximate yield of hydrogen peroxide and ozone (neglecting the catalytic effect of the vessel itself in destroying them) was obtained as follows:—A steel cylinder of an internal diameter 1½" and a foot long was capped at both ends by reducing sockets, one having an insulated platinum wire introduced for the purpose of supplying the heating source. Both ends had stopcocks and lead-outs and the apparatus was tested for gas tightness before the inflammable mixture was exploded in it. The explosion vessel was first filled with water and then the gas mixture was introduced by displacement of water. After explosion, the stopcock at one end was opened, keeping the end dipped into a solution of potassium iodide. The solution was well shaken in the explosion tube, run out into a beaker, the explosion vessel was repeatedly washed with water, and the whole solution titrated by means of a *N*-100 sodium thiosulphate solution. 315 C.c. of a gas mixture having equal volumes of hydrogen and oxygen in it, corresponded to 0.3 to 0.4 c.c. of *N*/100 thiosulphate solution. The mixture containing one volume of hydrogen and half a volume of oxygen similarly exploded, curiously liberating no iodine, although traces of both hydrogen peroxide and ozone were obtained in the explosion of the same mixture in soap bubbles.

The formation of hydrogen peroxide and ozone in soap bubble explosions was detected by introducing test papers into the

stem of the thistle funnel, or by interposing the corresponding test solution in the system. The reagents used for the purpose were an alcoholic solution of tetramethyldi-*p*-diaminodiphenyl methane (a name abbreviated to tetramethyl base), and a solution containing a mixture of ferric chloride and potassium ferricyanide (Arnold and Mentzel, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1824; Kaiser and McMaster *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1908, 39, 96). Oxy-hydrogen mixtures in the ratio of 8:2 or 7:3 gave no test for hydrogen peroxide or ozone. In 3:2, 2:1, and 1:1 mixtures both ozone and hydrogen peroxide are present in increasing quantities when such mixtures are exploded. This shows the formation of ozone when hydrogen is burnt which is ascribed to wrong observation by some.

Although under strictly identical conditions, reproducible ignition temperatures are obtainable by this method, the temperature depends on the length and shape of the wire and varies considerably, amounting from 200° to 300° at times. With platinum, the surface seems to affect the temperature; thus a 5" wire which had been in use for over a year, could ignite large soap bubbles at a constant temperature of 618°, whilst a new 6" wire ignited bubbles of identical size at the constant temperature of 355°. The catalytic nature of the surface is rendered further evident when the surface of the wire is roughened by rubbing with emery paper, or dipped in platinic chloride solution and ignited afterwards by passing a strong current. In both cases, there is a distinct drop in the ignition temperature.

Gas mixture ($H_2:O_2$)=1:1. Vol. of the bubble = 40 c.c.

Exp. I.			Exp. II.			
	Angle.	Length.	Temp.	Angle.	Length.	Temp.
New wire	30°	2"	570	60°	1½"	564°
Roughened wire	"	"	533°	"	"	545°
Platinised wire	"	"	500°	"	"	527°

It was found that the ignition temperature of small bubbles was greater than that of larger bubbles but as the volume increases further, the ignition temperature approaches a constant value as may be seen from Fig. 2. This is important both from the theoretical as also from the practical points of view. It would appear that approximately 500 c.c. is the critical volume at or beyond which

FIG. 2.

there is no change in the ignition temperature for the same ignition source under any particular set of conditions. A perceptible lag is noticed in the experiments with larger bubbles. This may be compared to the stationary stage of a chain reaction, whilst the explosion to the non-stationary stage (Hinshelwood, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, A, 122, 610). In ordinary language, one could say that the catalytic reaction initiated in the preflame period, being exothermic, affords sufficient heat to accelerate the chemical reaction to the stage of explosion, the large size of the bubble imparting to it a more insulated condition and hence a lowered ignition temperature. An alternative explanation, both as regards the constancy of ignition temperature as also its lowering, may be found in the reduced thickness of the soap film with increase in the size of the bubbles. As this would mean virtually the non-existence of any dividing septum between the gas volume and the source of ignition, a uniform ignition temperature is to be expected. This does not explain the remarkably

low temperature of ignition, for which we have to depend upon the preflame period or the generally insulated nature of the soap bubbles when they are large. In fact, to these conditions must be added also the catalytic behaviour of the wires themselves.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(1) Coil on silica strip. Length of pt. wire, 6". Vol. of the gas mixture, 35 c.c.

Comp. of gas mixture (H : O)	7 : 3	2 : 1	3 : 2	1 : 1	2 : 3.
Temp.	712°	708°	720°	750°	792°.

(2) Coil on mica strip. Length of pt. wire, 6". Vol. of the gas mixture, 35 c.c.

Comp. of gas mixture (H : O)	9 : 1	8 : 2	7 : 3	2 : 1	3 : 2	1 : 1	2 : 3.
Temp.	747°	749°	750°	754°	757°	758°	765°.

(3) Point source. Angle of the point 30° (approx.). Vol. of the gas mixture, 35 c.c. Length of the pt. wire, 6".

Comp. of gas mixture (H : O)	7 : 3	2 : 1	3 : 2	1 : 1	2 : 3.
Temp.	627°	616°	568°	605°	616°.

(4) Point source. Angle at the point 90° (approx.). Vol. of the gas bubble, 35 c.c. Length of the pt. wire, 6".

Comp. of gas mixture (H : O)	7 : 3	2 : 1	3 : 2	1 : 1	2 : 3
Temp.	665°	642°	628°	607°	609°

(5) Point source. Angle 120° (approx.) Length of the platinum wire, 6". Volume of the gas bubble, 35 c.c.

Comp. of gas mixture (H : O)	3 : 2	1 : 1	2 : 3	3 : 7
Temp.	650°	647°	639°	726°

(6) Point source. Angle at the point, 90°. Length of the platinum wire (new) 2½". In this experiment, the results of which are shown in Fig. 2 (curve 8) the change of the ignition temperature with the change of volume of the soap bubble was investigated, the composition of the gas mixture being as 1 : 1 of hydrogen and oxygen.

(7) Point source. Angle 90° . Length of the platinum wire (new), $4\frac{1}{2}$ ". Volume of the gas bubble, 35.0 c.c. Composition of the mixture, 1:1. Ignition temperature 538° . The influence of the length of the wire is very clear from the above data, as with a $2\frac{1}{2}$ " wire (Expt. 8) for the same composition and volume, the ignition temperature was only 465° .

(8) Coil on silica strip. Length of platinum wire 9". With a 1:1 mixture of hydrogen and oxygen, ignition temperatures, 775° , 701° , 668° , 656° were obtained for volumes 35, 150, 250 and 350 c.c. respectively.

(9) Coil on silica strip. Length of the wire, 5". Composition of the gas mixture 1:1. The results of this experiment are shown in Fig 2 (curve 11).

(10) Coil on silica strip. Length of the platinum wire, 6", but the wire was new. The composition of the gas mixture, the same as before, *i.e.*, 1:1. Fig. 2 (curve 12).

(11) Point source. Angle 30° approx. Length of the platinum wire (new), 6". Composition of the gas mixture 1:1. Fig. 2 (curve 13).

From Fig. 2, the attaining of a constant ignition temperature after the bubble has reached a volume of about 500 c.c. is seen.

Reproducibility of results is evident from the following experiments.

- (a) Point source, angle 30° , 6" pt. wire, 0.2mm. diam.
(b) 150 c.c. bubble exploded at 551° .
(c) After two months with same wire and 30° angle, 150 c.c. bubble exploded at 550° .
- (a) $2\frac{1}{2}$ " wire, diam. 0.2mm., point source, angle 90° . 100 c.c. bubble exploded at 318° .
(b) $2\frac{1}{2}$ " wire taken from the same reel as (a) with point source, angle 90° exploded at 320° .

Summary.

The results recorded in this paper and the previous one (Sen and Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 441) enable us to judge the reliability of the present method for determining the ignition point of inflammable gas mixtures. There can be no doubt that with the same arrangement the ignition temperature is sharp and entirely reproducible. Increment in the volume of the soap bubbles containing the inflammable mixtures, lowers the ignition point

up to a volume of 500 c.c. ; the ignition point remaining constant with larger volumes, a slight lag in the explosion being noticed. The influence of the composition is not so marked. The most important factor is the nature of the platinum surface. Experiments are, however, in progress to see if any additional information on this point is available. There is an important aspect of explosion which has been brought about by these experiments: the lowest ignition temperature is influenced by catalysis so considerably that the commonly accepted values of ignition temperatures of inflammable gas mixtures offer no indication of safety in technical accidents, where catalysing sources are frequent. Then the question of preflame period is important as at considerably lower temperatures ignitions have been initiated through protracted warming. Incidentally, the production of H_2O_2 and O_3 in hydrogen oxygen explosions and a few conditions of their production have been investigated.

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